

D5.11 Report on a Stakeholder Conference Workpackage 5

Responsible Partner: BfR, SSI

Contributing partners: ISS, University of Surrey

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Introduction

The Stakeholder Conference with the title “Collaborating to face future European One Health challenges” was held from the 19th to the 21st of June 2023 at the Museum of Natural Sciences of Brussels, Belgium. It provided a unique possibility for a wide range of stakeholders of the One Health arena to meet and discuss the status of European One Health today, in addition to the challenges of tomorrow.

The organisation of the conference was led by One Health EJP WP5, with major support from the Stakeholder Conference Working Group (SCoWG). The SCoWG was composed of selected One Health EJP Project Management Team (PMT) members and collaborators as well as the Communications Team, who took also care of the visual identity of the conference. The SCoWG met once or twice per month, for a total of 15 times, to discuss and take decisions on the conference, both on the scope, the contents, and its practical and logistical aspects.

The conference was organised as a hybrid event in order to have the maximum outreach. Overall, 965 people registered (912 registrations using the online form, and 53 additional registrations via direct contact with the organisers). 122 people attended on-site.

The feedback about the event was highly positive. The success of the event was seen by the high interest of the participants, the lively discussions during, aside and after the conference and the feedback received. This is reflected in the interests in the communication activities (e.g. a high level of engagement with social media posts on Twitter and LinkedIn.) which accompanied the meeting, and requests for providing the slides or recordings.

Background and aims

One Health EJP WP5 (Science to Policy Translation) focuses its efforts on the interaction with stakeholders, with main focus on European and international policy/decision makers. Targeted dissemination and mutual support activities have in the first place focused on those organisations that are part of the Stakeholders Committee of One Health EJP: ECDC, EFSA, EEA, EMA, FAO, WOA, and WHO/EURO. Additional activities (e.g. Dissemination Workshops) have been dedicated to inform national stakeholders, and, in collaboration with the Communications Team, to other interested parties traditionally not associated with the One Health EJP.

To achieve impact of the outcomes resulting from the One Health EJP on policy and science, but also on society and economy, the consortium set up mechanisms for effective dissemination to a wide range of interested parties (organisations, associations etc. beyond those involved in the Stakeholders Committee of the One Health EJP). During the final year of the project, the One Health EJP provided a platform to the vast network of and around the One Health EJP consortium to discuss the future of One Health in Europe, as well as the sustainability of the One Health EJP initiatives: the One Health EJP Stakeholder Conference “Collaborating to face future European One Health challenges”.

The aim of the conference was two-fold, and the event succeeded in delivering on both aims:

1. Dissemination for gaining impact

The conference was an opportunity to feedback to the community the solutions that the 30 joint projects and other activities of the One Health EJP developed since 2018, working together across sectors and borders, to improve the detect-prevent-respond capacity of European countries. The conference highlighted the impact that the One Health EJP activities had at the scientific (e.g. generation of new knowledge, capacity building, cross-sectoral harmonisation) and policy levels (e.g. support to evidence-based decision making, advocacy of One Health

approach). In addition, the conference was an opportunity to disseminate solutions and tools to a wide and diverse audience, supporting the achievement of long-term economic impact, e.g. with tools to enhance the sustainability of production, which could attract the interest of the private sector. Impact at the societal level was also highlighted e.g. by showcasing the improvement of health and food safety, the strengthening of trust between citizens and scientists, and the good use of EU funding. Last, but not least, the conference was an opportunity to discuss the sustainability of the One Health EJP consortium in general, and specifically the solutions that have been developed .

2. **Reflecting and shaping European One Health**

The ambitious conference programme brought together representatives of a wide variety of stakeholders, for example EC Directorate Generals, EU agencies, international organisations, consumer associations, other One Health projects, the private sector, NGOs, and the press. This provided a unique opportunity for representatives of decision-making bodies to discuss with representatives of other stakeholder groups the needs and challenges of future One Health initiatives. Indeed, similarly to other events of the One Health EJP (notably the Stakeholder Committee Meetings), this conference was also seen as a high-level forum to reflect on the current status of European One Health, and to shape its future.

Shaping the conference scope and target audiences

1. Preparatory exchanges with the Stakeholders Committee

Discussion around the content and aim of the conference started early, with exchanges within the PMT and between the One Health EJP and its stakeholders. Notably, in the Stakeholders Committee Meetings of 2021 and 2022, representatives of European and international organisations highlighted a number of aspects important for the programme, including the need to include representatives of NGOs and of the environmental sector.

2. Target audience

The Stakeholder Conference brought together European and international institutions and a wide range of other parties, such as representatives from civil society and the private sector. More specifically, the target audience included:

- Departments and executive agencies of the European Commission
- Agencies of the European Union
- One Health and other scientific initiatives
- Associations dealing with human, animal, and environmental health from the private sector, citizen, farmers, and patients associations
- Industry representatives
- General and specialised press

Given the focus on outcomes and impact, the audience did not require particular technical background to follow the discussion.

Accommodating such a wide audience was possible due to the hybrid nature of the conference, which posed no restrictions in terms of the audience following the event online (see section “Registration”).

Programme structure

The programme was divided in three running themes, which provided a fil rouge to follow throughout the conference, starting from the current status of One Health in Europe, and finishing with discussions its future. The focus was on the EU, with sessions dealing directly with EU issues, or highlighting the relation between global issues and the EU. In the preparatory phase, the agenda (Annex 1) was extensively discussed within the SCoWG, and carefully shaped to reflect the objectives of the conference.

The narrative followed the following running themes:

- **One Health in Europe.** This was the theme of the first day (19th of June), which opened the conference. The objective was to set the basis to understand the status of the current cross-sectoral collaboration, and how European One Health moved from theory to practice. The conference opened with welcome messages from the Director Generals of the two One Health EJP’s coordinating partners: ANSES and Sciensano. Due to the wide audience, not necessarily familiar with the One Health approach, the concept of One Health was then introduced, as well as the One Health EJP. This first part of the conference included a panel discussion with representatives of relevant EC DGs: AGRI, ENV, HEALTH, and RTD, as well as a talk highlighting the scientific and policy impact of the One Health EJP.

- **One Health in practice.** This was the theme of the first part of the second day (20th of June). Initially the need for cross-sectoral solutions from the EC point of view was presented, as well as how the One Health EJP addressed this need. It highlighted the impact and benefit of individual One Health solutions and initiatives, including their short and long-term effects and impacts.
- **Beyond classic One Health.** This was the theme of the second part of the second day. The objective was to set the stage for a new One Health activity, going beyond the traditional view of it being merely the collaboration between the human and animal health sector. A bold, new European One Health approach was discussed, that would, for example, take increasingly into account the needs of the civil society, tackle global health issues, and strengthen its environmental pillar. This part of the conference included a panel discussion where representatives of consumer associations, behavioural scientists, and experts in communication discussed the concerns of civil society and consumers, and how to include those better in the One Health agenda.
- **The future.** This was the theme of the last day of the conference (21st June). After having discussed the need and benefits of cross-sectoral collaboration, and having already stepped into the future with the theme “beyond classic One Health”, the objective of this theme was to steer the future European One Health direction, for example by highlighting the need of a more inclusive approach. This theme included two notable panel discussions. In the first, “An inclusive One Health”, representatives of the environmental sector, social scientists and representatives of pharma industry and of veterinarians’ organisations, got together to discuss the One Health initiatives of tomorrow, that should be ready to welcome the contribution from the various relevant sectors. In the second panel discussion, representatives of EU Agencies dealing with One Health (EEA, EFSA, ECDC, and EMA) discussed cross-agency collaboration, and what initiatives we can expect in the future, starting from [previous Agencies’ reflections](#) on the EU One Health agenda.

The conference closed with discussions around the sustainability of One Health EJP - which will end in September 2023 - its network, and its developed solutions. Central role in the sustainability of One Health EJP activities will be taken by the [Med-Vet-Net Association](#): an integrated European network of public and academic institutions with national reference functions in the medical/public health (Med) and food/veterinary (Vet) domains, fostering One Health research on zoonotic infectious diseases and AMR, and pursuing integration of expertise and harmonization of methodologies to reinforce the joint EU capacity to prevent, detect and control zoonoses and AMR.

Side event: WP7 workshop on institutionalization of One Health

After the conference, during the afternoon of the 21st of June, a workshop on the institutionalization of One Health was held, organised by the WP7 Sustainability team. This in person, by-invitation-only event involved an interactive discussion among One Health stakeholders and took place in the same location as the main conference, the Museum of Natural Sciences of Brussels.

The aim of the workshop was to prepare a roadmap document on the institutionalisation of One Health. The document is intended to be an operational tool and a guidance for countries deciding to implement a system to pursue a more effective and comprehensive health protection in a broader sense, according to the principles laid down by the One Health approach.

The workshop included an introductory session with a keynote speech given by Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, who presented the results of the [SUSTAIN](#) project and aspects of the implementation of the One Health approach in three EU Member States, and three major discussion sessions:

- One statement-driven discussion forum with five panellists from several EU member states, where a One Health scheme is in place to tackle health protection
- One session addressing the One Health EJP achievements that can represent operational components of the roadmap
- A general discussion with all the participants with the goal of identifying the ‘missing tiles’ to complete the picture of a complete One Health.

The agenda is given in Annex 4, and a report dedicated to the WP7 workshop on institutionalization of One Health will be published separately.

Invited speakers to the Stakeholder Conference

1. Internal One Health EJP speakers

Speakers internal to the One Health EJP included scientists from JIPs and JRPs, and PMT members.

PMT members talked about the value and impact of the One Health EJP as a whole: its funding to respond to specific needs of the EC, its implementation and growth, its scientific and educational activities, and its impact at the scientific and policy level.

Scientists of the JIPs and JRPs went into detail on how the solutions developed within their respective projects tackled the issues of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance, and emerging threats, with the common aim to improve the detect-prevent-response capacity of Europe.

These short presentations were ordered following the Integrative Strategy Matrix below, representing the Prevent – Detect – Respond chain.

Project representatives selected key outputs from their projects, presented as case studies. They briefly described the expected outcomes, as well as the short- and long-term impact. To appeal to the whole audience, the presentations focused on the impact and benefit that the presented solutions bring when applied.

2. External speakers

External speakers were invited to contribute with their knowledge on strategic directions of the organisations they represent, and because of their familiarity with the One Health approach.

As it can be seen from the agenda (Annex 1), speakers and panellists included representatives of EU institutions (DGs, EU Agencies, Presidency of the Council of the EU), international organisations (WHO, FAO), professional and consumer associations (FVE, BEUC), pharma industry association (Animalhealth Europe for the animal side, Swedish Pharmaceutical Industry Association/ EFPIA/AESGP for the human side), and other initiatives related with One Health (Biodiversa+, Safe Consume, One Health Social Sciences).

Logistical arrangements

1. Selection of venue

Due to its strategic position, and being the location of many relevant organisations, the conference was held in Brussels. As many invited speakers and a substantial part of registered audience were already based in Brussels, there was an advantage of lowering the costs, facilitating participation in person, and avoiding unnecessary travel-related emissions.

2. Format of the event

Given the wide target audience and considering the limited capacity of the venue as well as environmental aspects and inclusiveness, it was decided to organise the conference in hybrid form (the side event was in-person only). Audience online had the possibility to interact with the speakers and with their peers through a chat and a Q&A function. The hybrid nature of the event facilitated also the participation of speakers, that had the possibility to give talks and participate in panel discussions in remote.

The event had two formats of sessions: classic talks supported by slides, and panel discussions. For both, a moderator was in charge of keeping the time and moderating the discussion. A specific moderation team was in charge of managing the questions posed online.

Registration and selection of participants

1. Registration

To respect the privacy of the registered participants, minimal information was requested at registration.

Regarding the application for on-site participation, due to limited capacity of the venue, the SCoWG took the liberty of selecting among interested participants those present on-site. Submission for on-site participation closed on the 7th of April 2023, and responses were sent on the 14th of April 2023. Applicants not selected for on-site participation received the link to join the conference online.

Regarding the participation online, registration counted as automatic acceptance. Deadline for registration of online participation was the 12th of June 2023. Additional registrations were possible via direct contact with the organisers.

All the participants (both on-site and online) received the link to join the conference online to the provided email address. This allowed also the audience present in person to ask questions in written form online, should they have chosen to.

The event was free of charge for all the participants, both on-site and online.

2. Criteria for selection of on-site participants

Speakers, PMT members, and delegates invited to the side event (workshop on institutionalisation of One Health) were automatically accepted. For the remaining ones, the SCoWG aimed to achieve regional and gender balance, and to include policy makers, press, industry and NGOs. If many people from a single organisation registered, the selection considered also if a line of motivation was written to explain their interest.

3. Composition of audience

965 people registered to the event (912 using the online form, and 53 via direct contact with the organisers). 122 were present on-site, and between about 140 to 300 participated online. The figure below shows the distribution across the sectors of the registrations (please note that because it was possible to select multiple sectors, the sum exceeds the total number of registrations).

While the preponderant sectors were One Health, public health, animal health and food safety, 144 people selected environmental or ecosystem health, and 48 social sciences.

Communication and promotion

Promotion of the conference started early and was continuously adapted as organisation proceeded. The first social media posts (on Twitter and LinkedIn) and website Latest News post to promote conference registration were disseminated on 1st February 2023.

1. General promotion and dissemination

The One Health EJP Communications Team was mainly responsible for the general dissemination via website, the newsletter and social media.

A webpage dedicated to the event (<https://onehealthjep.eu/outcomes/science-to-policy-translation/stakeholder-conference-2023>) was created in the website of the One Health EJP. The webpage included all the necessary information, including a save the date flyer (Annex 2).

A number of dissemination mechanism were deployed to reach the relevant audiences. These mechanisms included a social media campaign that focused on engaging with the different audiences invited to attend the conference (on the platforms of Twitter, LinkedIn), articles on the One Health website and newsletters, and a Conference Announcement as a blog post (Annex 3). A [post-event blog post](#) celebrating the success of the Conference was added to the website with associated social media posts subsequently disseminated.

During the week of the conference, the Communications Team created and disseminated 21 tweets and 4 LinkedIn posts, which led to excellent engagement responses on Twitter (85 inbound messages, 338 post likes, 963 post engagements and 3.9% post engagement rate) and LinkedIn (56 post reactions and 5.37% post engagement rate).

2. Dissemination to specific audiences

WP5 Science to Policy Translation and WP1 Coordination teams were mainly responsible for targeted dissemination to specific stakeholders, mostly via direct emails. This kind of targeted dissemination required the collection and categorisation of the target audiences in specific groups (e.g. national policy makers, EC DGs, projects, associations, private sector, NGOs), and the identification of putative interest that each group could have in the conference. Based on these interests, a targeted message per group was drafted, that was used in targeted emails, as well as in social media campaigns.

Key lessons learnt

Below some main messages of the One Health EJP Stakeholder Conference are shown. Additional dedicated communication is planned to target specific audiences.

1. Theme “One Health in Europe”:

- Only a cross-sectoral/holistic/collaborative approach, that considers humans, animals, and environment, can have long term impact on modern health challenges.
- EU high policy level supports One Health collaboration and setting up a legal basis for cross-sectoral collaboration.
- One Health approach is implemented in a number of Commission’s policies, under all the relevant DGs.

2. Theme “One Health in practice”:

- One Health EJP addressed the needs identified by the EC of implementing a cross-sectoral programme on AMR, foodborne zoonoses, and emerging infectious threats.
- One Health solutions bring benefit when implemented. A number of examples were given.

3. Theme “Beyond classic One Health”:

- Engagement with civil society is crucial to understand citizens’ priorities and perceptions, and to design behaviourally informed strategies.
- In a globalised world, national and regional One Health issues are global issues needing coordination and governance.
- There is no complete protection of human and animal health without protection of environment and biodiversity.

4. Theme “The future”:

- One Health will have to increasingly embrace new sectors and fields (e.g. social sciences) and be open to collaborations (private sector, professional organisations).
- Additional efforts in cross-sectoral communication are needed.
- EU Agencies support the One Health approach and, looking towards the future, updated on the newly established [One Health cross-agency task force](#).

Annex 1: Public agenda of the Stakeholder Conference

A One Health EJP conference

Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe

MUSEUM OF NATURAL SCIENCES, BRUSSELS
19-21 JUNE 2023 - hybrid format

During this **three day conference** we will reflect on the future of One Health with a particular focus on Europe, together with high level speakers from influential organisations and institutions.

We will also discuss the impact achieved by the One Health EJP during the five years of its existence.

MONDAY 19th JUNE

Theme: One Health in Europe

14.00-15.30 CEST *Registration and coffee*

15.30-16.20

Welcome and introduction

Moderator: Hein Imberechts

Arnaud Callegari, One Health EJP Project Coordinator, [ANSES](#)

Benoît Vallet, Director General of [ANSES](#)

Christian Léonard, Director General of [Sciensano](#)

Societal impact of One Health issues: a focus on education

Roberto La Ragione, One Health EJP [Education and Training](#), [University of Surrey](#)

Introduction to One Health EJP

Hein Imberechts, One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator, [Sciensano](#)

16.20-17.15

One Health in Europe: from theory to practice

Moderator: Pikka Jokelainen

High-level round table panel discussion:

Irene Norstedt, Directorate-General for [Research and Innovation](#)

Roser Domenech, Directorate-General for [Health and Food Safety](#)

Kerstin Rosenow, Directorate-General for [Agriculture and Rural Development](#)

Veronica Manfredi, Directorate-General for [Environment](#)

Agnes-Marta Molnar, Directorate-General for the [Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority](#)

17.20-17.40

Break

17.40-18.20

Impact of the One Health EJP

Moderator: Ludovico Sepe

Scientific impact of the One Health EJP

Hein Imberechts, One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator, [Sciensano](#)

Impact of the One Health EJP towards stakeholders

Annemarie Käesbohrer, One Health EJP [Science to Policy Translation](#), [BfR](#)

18.30-20.30

Welcome cocktail

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19-21 JUNE 2023 - hybrid format

TUESDAY 20th JUNE

Theme: One Health in Practice

- 09.00-09.05 *CEST* Introduction to Day Two
Ludovico Sepe, One Health EJP [Science to Policy Translation](#), [BfR](#)
- 09.05-09.20 Point of view of the European Commission: why the One Health EJP was necessary and how it responded to identified needs by DG AGRI
Moderator: Hein Imberechts
Jean-Charles Cavitte, DG-Agriculture and Rural Development
- 09.20-09.30 History and context of the One Health EJP
Moderator: Hein Imberechts
Arnaud Callegari, One Health EJP Project Coordinator
- 09.30-10.50 One Health EJP contribution to cross sectoral harmonisation
Moderators: Karin Artursson and Dolores Gavier-Widén
- Presentations by One Health EJP Joint Integrative Projects:
Introduction to Joint Integrative Projects
Karin Artursson, One Health EJP [Joint Integrative Projects](#), [SVA](#)
- One Health EJP [COVRIN](#) project
Wim Van der Poel, [WUR](#)
- One Health EJP [MATRIX](#) project
Guido Benedetti, [SSI](#)
- One Health EJP [OH-HARMONY-CAP](#) project
Nadia Boisen, [SSI](#)
- One Health EJP [CARE](#) project
Mia Torpdahl, [SSI](#)
- One Health EJP [ORION](#) project
Matthias Filter, [BfR](#)
- One Health EJP [COHESIVE](#) project
Frits Vlaanderen, [RIVM](#)
- One Health EJP [Simulation Exercise](#)
Anna Omazic, [SVA](#)
- 10.50-11.20 *Coffee break*

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11.20-12.00	<p><i>CEST</i> One Health EJP contribution to tackling foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats <i>Moderators: Hein Imberechts and Pikka Jokelainen</i></p> <p>Presentations by One Health EJP Joint Research Projects: Introduction to Joint Research Projects Hein Imberechts, One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator, Sciensano</p> <p>One Health EJP ARDIG project Muna Anjum, APHA</p> <p>One Health EJP WORLDCOM project Arnoud Van Vliet, University of Surrey</p> <p>One Health EJP TOX-DETECT project Jacques-Antoine Hennekinne, ANSES</p>
12.00-13.00	<p><i>Lunch break</i></p>
13.00-14.20	<p>One Health EJP IDEMBRU project Claire Ponsart, ANSES</p> <p>One Health EJP MedVetKlebs project Sylvain Brisse, Pasteur Institute</p> <p>One Health EJP PARADISE project Simone Cacció, ISS</p> <p>One Health EJP TOXOSOURCES project Pikka Jokelainen, SSI</p> <p>One Health EJP MeME project Adriano Casulli, ISS</p> <p>One Health EJP FULL-FORCE project Pieter-Jan Ceysens, Sciensano</p> <p>One Health EJP DISCOVER project Tine Hald, DTU</p> <p>One Health EJP MoMIR-PPC project Philippe Velge, INRAE</p>
14.20-14.35	<p>The mechanisms in place to monitor the successful implementation of One Health EJP <i>Moderator: Hein Imberechts</i> Amanda Jane Ozin-Hofsaess, European Research Executive Agency</p>

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14.35-15.00 CEST Introduction to JRC BREATH
Moderator: Hein Imberechts
Sandra Coecke, Ana Ruiz-Moreno, and Antonio Marchini, [Joint Research Centre](#)

15.00-15.30 *Coffee break*

Theme: Beyond Classic One Health

15.30-16.30 Concerns of civil society and consumers
Moderator: Ludovico Sepe
High-level round table panel discussion:
Domagoj Vrbos, [The European Food Safety Authority](#)
Cortney Price, [Food and Agricultural Organisation](#)
Solveig Langsrud, [SafeConsume](#)
Camille Perrin, [BEUC](#)

16.30-17.00 Strengthening of the Global Health Security Architecture – update on global and regional processes
Moderator: Dolores Gavier-Widén
Sandra Lindmark, [WHO Regional Office for Europe](#)

17.00-17.20 The climate-biodiversity-Onehealth nexus, and the role of nature-based solutions
Moderator: Annemarie Käsbohrer
Hilde Eggermont, [Biodiversa+](#)

17.20 *End of day two*

WEDNESDAY 21th JUNE

Theme: The Future

08.50-08.55 Introduction to Day Three
Ludovico Sepe, One Health EJP [Science to Policy Translation](#), [BfR](#)

09.00-09.45 An inclusive One Health encompassing environment, social sciences, and the private sector
Moderator: Roberto La Ragione
High-level round table panel discussion:
Dario Piselli, [European Environment Agency](#)
Severine Thys, [One Health Social Sciences](#)
Roxane Feller, [Animalhealth Europe](#)
Despoina Iatridou, [Federation of Veterinarians of Europe](#)

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09.45-10.30 CEST	New One Health trajectories of EU Agencies <i>Moderator: Pikka Jokelainen</i> High-level round table panel discussion: Mike Catchpole, European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control Carlos das Neves, The European Food Safety Authority Dario Piselli, European Environment Agency Ivo Claassen, European Medicines Agency
10.30-11.00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11.00-11.15	One Health related activities in the veterinary context during the Swedish Presidency <i>Moderator: Karin Artursson</i> Lena Hellqvist Björnerot, Chief Veterinary Officer of the Sweden's Presidency of the Council of the EU
11.15-11.40	What is the future of the One Health EJP? <i>Moderator: Dolores Gavier-Widén</i> Arjen van de Giessen, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
11.40-12.00	Closing remarks and lessons learnt Arnaud Callegari, One Health EJP Project Coordinator, ANSES Hein Imberechts, One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator, Sciensano
12.00-13.00	<i>Lunch break</i>
13.00-17.30	Workshop on institutionalisation of One Health <i>By invitation only</i>

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Notes: 1) No representative of HERA attended the panel discussion on 19th June at 16:20 “One Health in Europe”; 2) one additional panellist of the session on 21st June at 09:00 “an inclusive One Health” was Bengt Mattson (Swedish Pharmaceutical Industry Association (LIF)/EFPIA/AESGP).

Annex 2: Save the date flyer

Save the Date!

Collaborating to Face Future One Health Challenges in Europe

a One Health conference

Date: 19th to 21st June 2023

Location: [Museum of Natural Sciences](#), Brussels

Audience: Departments and executive agencies of the European Commission;
Agencies of the European Union;
One Health and other scientific initiatives;
Associations for human, animal, and environmental health - private sector,
citizen, farmers, or patients associations;
General and specialised press.

Website: [for further information](#)

Registration: [here](#)

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Annex 3: Conference Announcement

Conference Announcement for the One Health European Joint Programme Conference June 2023 for stakeholders

The One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP) is delighted to announce that the final international stakeholder conference “Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe” will be held in Belgium.

The One Health EJP Conference 2023 will take place in Brussels from the 19th to 21st June 2023. This three-day hybrid event will be held both online and in-person at the inspiring [Museum of Natural Sciences](#) (Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences). Since Brussels is the centre for European Union politics and governance, it provides an ideal location for the final conference focused on addressing One Health challenges in Europe now and in the future. Conference attendance is open to a variety of different stakeholders, including those from public and private sector organisations across Europe and globally. Our Consortium looks forward to welcoming 165 delegates for on-site participation and an unlimited number of online attendees for this exciting international event. Online registration remains open on our [website](#) until 12th June 2023.

Our societies face multiple health threats from zoonotic infectious diseases (transmitted from animals to humans), antimicrobial resistance (AMR), climate change, biodiversity loss and environmental degradation. The severity of these emerging threats and their impacts on people and non-human species will increase over this decade unless the One Health approach is more widely adopted. One Health is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems. Whilst many European and international organisations have already adopted this holistic approach to be better prepared to prevent, predict, detect, and respond to global health challenges – further progress in its wider application is essential.

Since 2018, The One Health EJP has embraced the One Health approach in its collaborative partnership with 44 institutions across Europe in the fields of public health, animal health and food safety, including the Med-Vet-Net Association. The Consortium has established One Health networks and the scientific

research has developed tools to tackle AMR, foodborne zoonoses and emerging threats. [Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe](#) conference will share One Health EJP-devised solutions to improve the detect-prevent-response capacity of European countries and highlight the impact of our programme.

Invited speakers include high-level representatives from influential organisations and One Health EJP members who will provide their insights on One Health in Europe. Conference sessions will focus on what is currently being done and what we can expect from future European One Health initiatives to address the complex health challenges that arise.

The conference will be divided into four main themes: One Health in Europe, One Health in Practice, Beyond Classic One Health, and the Future of One Health. Speakers will discuss how the theory of One Health may be put into practice at the EU and national levels. Representatives from the [European Commission](#) and from European Agencies ([EFSA](#), [ECDC](#), [EEA](#), [EMA](#)) will offer their perspectives on One Health policy. One Health EJP members will explain the relevance and impact of our cross-sectoral activities to address European health needs.

Panel discussions will examine the concerns of the public and consumers, highlight the challenges of climate change and biodiversity loss and consider how to better include the environment, social sciences, public sector in future One Health initiatives. Invited speakers for these panel discussions include representatives from the [UN Food and Agriculture Organisation](#), [SafeConsume](#), [BEUC](#), [Biodiversa+](#), [One Health Social Sciences Initiative](#), [AnimalhealthEurope](#) and [Federation of Veterinarians of Europe](#).

The aims of this conference are to provide engaging and progressive discussions on the future of One Health to a broad global audience, whilst also highlighting the legacy of One Health EJP's work.

More information about the One Health EJP can be found on our [website](#).

[Collaborating to face future One Health challenges in Europe](#) provides registration information and the conference agenda.

Annex 4: Agenda of the WP7 workshop on institutionalisation of One Health

Part of One Health EJP Stakeholder Conference

Workshop on Institutionalisation of One Health

MUSEUM OF NATURAL SCIENCES, BRUSSELS

21 JUNE 2023 - in person

13.00 CEST	<p>Welcome and purpose of the workshop Stefano Morabito, One Health EJP Sustainability, Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS), Italy Dolores Gavier-Widén, One Health EJP Sustainability, National Veterinary Institute (SVA), Sweden</p>
13.10	<p>Institutionalisation of One Health: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda Stefano Morabito</p>
13.25	<p>OHEJP SUSTAIN project: state of play on One Health institutionalisation Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden, Roskilde University, Denmark</p>
13.50	<p>State of play of One Health institutionalisation: statement-driven open discussion forum Moderator: Dolores Gavier-Widén <i>Panellists (each will make short statements on the level One Health is institutionalised in their countries):</i> Henrik Ullum, Denmark Ann Lindberg, Sweden Myriam Sneyers, Belgium Umberto Agrimi, Italy</p>
14.50	<p><i>Break</i></p>
15.10	<p>Components of the Institutionalisation of One Health produced in the One Health EJP activities</p> <p>Capacity building: knowledge, achievements of Joint Research Projects; current situation and future needs Hein Imberechts, One Health EJP Scientific Coordinator, Sciensano</p> <p>Capacity building: resources, achievements of Joint Integrative Projects; current situation and future needs Karin Artusson, One Health EJP WP4 Leader, National Veterinary Institute (SVA), Sweden</p> <p>Capacity building: training and education programmes; current situation and future needs Roberto La Ragione, One Health EJP Education and Training, University of Surrey</p> <p>Science-to-policy transfer: current situation and future needs Annemarie Käesbohrer, One Health EJP Science to Policy Translation, BfR</p> <p>Stakeholders' expectations: input from the Stakeholder Conference Ludovico Sepe, One Health EJP Science to Policy Translation, BfR</p> <p><i>Questions</i></p>
16.00	<p>The 'missing tiles': group discussion Roundtable discussion on the possible Items of the institutionalisation domain uncovered by the One Health EJP and how the roadmap document should be shaped</p>
17.00	<p>Conclusions and proposal for the roadmap document Stefano Morabito Dolores Gavier-Widén</p>
17.30	<p><i>Close</i></p>

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